

THE CHANGING ROLE OF WOMEN LEADERSHIP IN RURAL LOCAL SELF-GOVERNMENT

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Abstract

India is a country of villages even today almost 70% of the people live in villages. Therefore more important has been given to government instructions in rural areas. These local self-government bodies are referred to as Panchayat. State system in the view of development of the rural people and direct participation in their local administration. The most fundamental political institution the relationship between local government instruction and democratic government is very close power. The local self-governing bodies that provide civil in fraction for local self-governing bodies. The system that administrative heads, sarpanch and presidents in some places. The chairman are elected from the elected representatives, while in some places the elected directly from the electorate in our country of India. The companies to royal women builded power, but they were few in number. The common man was hundreds of Kos away from it. After independence Gandhi and Nehru insist that common women should play their part in the development of the country. The concept of panchayat Raj was in shine. In the guiding principles of a constitution, the 73 constitutional amendment passed by the central government in 1993. It gives constitutional recognition to local self-governing bodies. According to the 73 and 74 amendment of the constitution one third of the total seats in all the local self-government bodies are reserve for women. However women who have been trapped in the heart of the child for long time have definitely gained a share of power in politics, but what are their rights, what positive role can women play in politics they have no idea that they can, that is why often their husbands, brothers, manage on there be half in such a way.

In the Indian constitution women have been given equal right to men in economic, social, and political Spheres. In addition to a green to this, It is the duty of the states to pay special attention to the development of women. In the society which has been exploited and marginalised for centuries considering. The article of the constitution India has been taken the lead in the world in providing equal rights to women and giving women the right to vote.

Keywords: Panchayat Raj, Role of Women in Panchayat Raj, Constitution, Women Rights.

Introduction:

Democratic governance is considered as an ideal form of governance after independence, India has also adopted a democratic system. In this system of government the ultimate power is in the hand of the people. Therefore the constitution give everyone the right to vote without any discrimination like religion, race, cast, language or reason, Panchayat Raj System was adopted to inculcate the principles of freedom, Equality, fraternity, justice and decentralisation of power through a democratic governance system. For the success of democratic governance. Participation of people is necessary therefore constitutionalist have adopted the path of democratic decentralization. But if we think about the whole world which is half of the society has been deprived of the political Sphere for many years.

The Indian constitution makers have adopted the policy of reservation to bring the backward sections of society into the mainstream although the principles of freedom equality. Equal opportunity was accepted in the Indian constitution there was no mentality to give equal opportunity to women. At the same time many movements arose at the international level to make women aware of their rights. Even if democracy was adopted in India after independence this centralisation of power was necessary to bring the governance system down to the grassroots level so then rural in India adopted the Panchayat Raj System. Panchayat Raj system also known as the father of local government for their act of 1919 and 1935 give a boost to local government bodies. After independence the constitution adopt the principle of democratic decentralization and includes the subject of local government in the state list letter in 1957 the Government of India established the Balwant Rai Mehta committee. According to the committee recommendation of the committee that three tier Panchayat Raj system was adopted in 1959. The Maharashtra government also try to make Panchayat Raj system more people oriented by establishing several committees. But in reality the local government bodies has less autonomy for financial matters they had to depend on the favour of the state's administration therefore to make these institutions efficient and to restore the constitutional status many intellectuals proposed the role of 64th Amendment Bill in 1989. But it was not pass for the same will regarding Panchayat Raj institution was introduced with reference to the 73rd constitutional amendment on 22nd December 1992 from 24th April 1993. This act came into effect all over India in order to decentralized power it is necessary to involve women to increase the participation of more people in this organisation. There for article 243 (W) of the

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constitution through the 73rd amendment reserve for women not less than one third of the seats to be filled by direct election in each local government body 33% of the seats were reserved for women institutions also got constitutional status a progressive. State like Maharashtra has provide for 50% reservation seat to increase the presentation of women reservation for women. In local government body was important day for women empowerment against this drop women's participation and leadership in local government organisation and gained importance.

Importance of research

Women has been directly participating in the political processing. The first general election in 1952 under the representation of the people Act the panchayat act in the Indian constitution. However if we think about the participation of women in local and parliamentary elections their contribution in the election was somewhat disappointing. But their participation was gradually increasing among the women who wear elected to parliament. It was found that they acted or influence of their leaders or husbands with less personality influence. Considering the active participation of women in parliament, it is very important to mention some women for example Indira Gandhi, Vijaya Lakshmi Pandit, Uma Bharti, Jay Lalita, SuchetaKriplani.

One third of the countries Gram Panchayat can take over government in Jilla Parishad, Nagar Parishad, Mahanagar Palika. Through this new role women can become more active in the development process of the country. They can implemented the development plans of their villages. District from their perspective due to the governments neglected to issues of local self-government bodies. Mahatma Gandhi's idea of village self-government the process of development has not been able to take that recent government targeted policy of participatory planning. Seat increasing women's participation due to reservation in education, reservation in job. The number of women is increasing and women are being empowered because of this participation of women in leadership has recently increase. More over the role of women in leadership is also changing due to social changes. A sociological study of the changing role of women leadership is going to be done in the present research.

Objectives:

The following objectives have been said for the present research

- 1) To make a sociological study of women leadership in rural local self-government bodies.
- 2) To study the changing role of women leadership in rural local self-government bodies.

3) To study the sociological problems faced by women leadership in rural local self-government bodies.

4) To suggest a solution plan to solve sociological problems faced by women leadership in local self-government bodies.

Hypothesis:

The following hypothesis have been formulated for the present research paper

1) Leadership development among women in local self-government bodies is necessary to overcome male dominated culture.

Research methods:

The main objectives is to explain the research methodology used to achieve the objects of the present research paper. The research presented is mainly based on primary and secondary data. In this research paper the research area is going to be collected an analysis from various local self-government bodies such as release Panchayat Samiti, district council, Municipal Corporation.

Secondary data will be collected on the basis of socio- economic review, district census, and manual government reports. Standard computer system will be used for data collection tabulation analysis thereof besides median frequency main percentage population correlation statistical tests. Statistical techniques will also be done to analyse the qualitative facts, tabulation analysis and presentation of the collected fact.

Panchayat Raj Institute in India

The 73th and 74th amendment (1993) of the Indian constitution have served as a breakthrough towards ensuring equal access and increased participation in political power structure for women. The PRIs and the local self-governments are actively involved in the implementation and execution of the national policy for women at grassroots level.

Panchayat Raj in Maharashtra state

Rural governors in India is based on panchayat Raj system. It is a three tier system, with the Zillah Perished, at the district level, blocks at the middle level and village council. At the lowest level it is governed under the Maharashtra JillaParishad and Panchayat Samiti Acts 1961' act of Maharashtra state.

Reservation to elected seats are Mandated by the constitution in the following pattern

- 1) One third of the total numbers of seats filled by direct election in the every panchayat are to be reserved for women. This is inclusive of the reservation provided for women belonging to the SC /STs article 234D.
- 2) Within the reservation provided for persons belonging to the SC/STs as detailed above not less than one third of the total number of seats that are reserved for different categories in each Panchayat are to be reserved for women belonging to the SC/ STs.

73rd constitutional amendment historical milestone for women's political participation.

To protect the interests of the disadvantaged segments of the population, notably women, the schedule castes (SC) and the schedule tribes (ST). To ensure their participation in democratic decentralization process. The 73rd and 74th constitutional amendment was passed with the provision of reservation on 23rd April 19 93 the act reserved one third of all seats in the local self-governing bodies for rural for all three levels of panchayats and urban areas (municipal body) representally for women and reservation for SC ST proportionate to their population. Though reservation for STs and SCs are in place in other elected bodies (National and state legislative assemblies) the 73rd amendment is the first one in India that mandated women's reservation in local body election Article 243 D of 73rd constitutional Amendment act covers, in detail the manner. In which reservations are to be provided to women and other belongings to the SC/ STs in local Panchayat election at all three levels.

WOMEN 'S STATUS IN INDIAN:

India's social and cultural structures are so hierarchical and discriminatory that minority groups continue to be excluded from decision making forums. Experience wide spread discrimination and disadvantage in this contacts the marginalisation of women from India's political sphere represents a major challenges. This challenge is, however, not limited to India's but it is a common concern in democracies around the world. Woman throw out the developing world are not only underrepresented in decision making bodies but there is widespread marginalization of women voters. Political activities more or women who are politically active

either as engage citizen. Elected representatives of on face discrimination harassment and violence at the hands of community member or even there on family and political parties.

In India which is the world's largest democracy equal rights and status for women are enshrined in the constitution adopted in 1950 after freedom was own from the British colonial powers the constitutional reflected the speed of the reported throughout the country.

Gender equality has a devastating impact on women's health will being and dignity it is also discrimination to social economic and political process.

One of the most effective ways of addressing gender inequalities and discrimination is to ensure women's active and direct participation in governance.

WOMEN 'S REPRESENTATION IN GOVERNANCE BODIES

Despite making of 48% of India's population and 47.5% of the registered voting population women currently hold only 11% of floor house set and 10.6% of upper house set in National parliament for the in 2012 only for women held ministerial positions this amount to a disappointing 9.8% of all ministerial roles.

The women's moment in India has been vocal in high lighting the marginalisation and discrimination that women face across the country and has demanded space within the political reservation.

The effect of women's movement the Government of India pass the 73rd and 74th amendment to the constitution in 1992. According to this amendment 33% of seats the reserve for women at the local level of politics there is it of this reservation is that women's actively participate in local governing bodies in higher. since the implementation of the reservation system women's political participate in local self-government.

Table 1: Percentage of Elected Women Representatives in Panchayats in Indian States

SR. No	States	Percentage	SR. No	States	Percentage
1	Andhra Pradesh	50	16	Manipur	50.69
2	Arunachal Pradesh	38.98	17	Odisha	52.68
3	Assam	56.6	18	Punjab	41.79
4	Bihar	52.2	19	Rajasthan	51.79
5	Chhattisgarh	54.78	20	Sikkim	50.3
6	Goa	36.72	21	Tamil Nadu	52.98
7	Haryana	42.12	22	Telangana	50.34
8	Himachal Pradesh	50.12	23	Tripura	45.23
9	Jammu & Kashmir	33.18	24	Uttar Pradesh	33.34
10	Gujarat	49.96	25	Uttarakhand	56.01
11	Jharkhand	51.57	26	West Bengal	51.42
12	Karnataka	50.05			
13	Kerala	52.41			
14	Madhya Pradesh	49.99			
15	Maharashtra	53.47			

Conclusion:

After 66 years of democracy India continuous to face many challenges in the democracy governance.

Women's marginalisation from political life is preventing them from participating in society as complete and equal citizen. This is also reduce the capacity of decision making bodies to effectively govern or address the needs and priorities of all members of the community. But it is possible to overcome the challenges so that everyone trigger lace of their gender and

participate in the governance process this will help India to look beyond the traditional patriarchal approach to government.

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Women Reservation Bill

Post Gandhi, India experienced centralisation of planning which resulted in higher inequalities in political decision making at the various levels while government was deeply concern of issues of gender equality to women were not always a part of such decision making Although, India has seen women participating in politics as the longest serving Prime minister, as chief minister of various States members in National parliaments and state legislative assembly enlarge number, yet the occurrence such events has not been commensurate to their population

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खडसे भा. कि. 2002 जाती व वर्ग आणि भारतीय आदिवासी यशवंतराव चव्हाण मुक्त विद्यापीठ नाशिक

पोले कांतराव प्रल्हादराव 2005 महाराष्ट्रातील पंचायत राज मधील महिला आरक्षणाची फलनिष्पत्ती लातूर जिल्ह्याचा अभ्यास अप्रकाशित शोध प्रबंध डॉक्टर बाबासाहेब आंबेडकर मराठवाडा विद्यापीठ औरंगाबाद